

Spotlight: Mapping Pakistan's Health System

A Landscape of Health Financing Governance
in Sindh Province, Pakistan

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

DHO	District Health Officer
EPHS	Essential Package of Health Services
GDP	gross domestic product
HBP	health benefits package
MoNHSRC	Ministry of National Health Services, Regulation and Coordination
NFC	National Finance Commission
NHA	National Health Accounts
OOP	out-of-pocket
PFM	public financial management
PHC	primary health care
PPHI	Peoples' Primary Healthcare Initiative
PPP	Public-Private Partnership
UHC	universal health coverage
UHC-BP	Universal Health Coverage-Benefit Package
WHO	World Health Organization

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Effective governance of health financing functions is essential for Sindh's progress toward universal health coverage, yet Sindh province faces critical structural and operational challenges that impede equitable healthcare financing. In Pakistan, the constitutional devolution of health responsibilities to provinces through the 18th Amendment to the Constitution has transferred authority without corresponding capacity development, creating a governance gap between formal responsibility and implementation capacity. These governance challenges manifest across all health financing functions—revenue raising, pooling, purchasing, and benefits design—requiring coordinated reform strategies rather than isolated interventions in specific components.

Sindh province operates without a comprehensive health financing policy or strategy, resulting in fragmented financing decisions and implementation approaches. There is no coherent framework to guide decision-making across the financing functions of revenue collection, pooling, purchasing, or designing benefits packages. This policy vacuum leads to ad hoc financing decisions driven by historical patterns, political considerations, and long-standing institutional practices rather than strategic priorities or evidence-based allocation criteria. The provincial Health Department has no dedicated structure to coordinate health financing functions. This results in significant inefficiencies, as the departments involved in health financing, such as Finance, Health, Planning and Development, and specialized agencies, operate with limited strategic alignment. The province's health financing governance remains heavily centralized, with district health authorities possessing limited financial autonomy despite their critical role in service delivery. These structural weaknesses create a fundamental disconnect between financing arrangements and population health needs, particularly for rural communities that face disproportionate financial burdens despite lower service utilization.

Revenue-raising governance in Sindh is constrained by the province's limited fiscal autonomy, with approximately 82% of its overall revenue derived from federal transfers that are not always aligned with provincial needs. This heavy fiscal dependence restricts Sindh's decision-making authority and limits the availability and flexibility of resources to meet local priorities, particularly in the health sector. Although the province has constitutional authority to expand its tax base, it has not fully exercised this power—especially for health—resulting in own-source revenues contributing only 18% of Sindh's total revenue. The absence of earmarked funding for health further weakens the sector's ability to compete for resources against other provincial priorities. Together, these governance and financing constraints have contributed to the dominance of out-of-pocket (OOP) spending, which constitutes about 55.4% of total health expenditure (THE) and 81% of private health expenditure in Sindh, one of the highest rates in the region. The resulting financial protection failure disproportionately affects rural households, which spend a higher percentage of their income on healthcare despite lower utilization rates compared to urban households.

Pooling arrangements remain underdeveloped, limiting the province's ability to achieve equitable resource distribution across the health system. The centralized pool of resources in Sindh—which depends on the transfer of general tax-based revenue from the federal government—offers the potential for a more equitable allocation of resources across the public sector. This single dominant pool could reduce the complexity and inefficiencies in the current fragmented health financing system if governed more effectively. Additionally, complementary smaller pools operated by social security institutions and voluntary insurance schemes remain disjointed from the main public pool, creating systemic inefficiencies without expanding effective coverage. These fragmented pooling arrangements fail to redistribute resources based on need, limit risk-sharing across population groups, and ultimately undermine the province's ability to advance toward universal health coverage despite the structural advantages of having a dominant central pool.

Purchasing remains predominantly passive, lacking institutional capacity and accountability mechanisms for strategic resource allocation. The allocation of health facility budgets is based on historical patterns and political influences rather than structured, needs-based approaches or

performance criteria. Despite the Public-Private Partnership Act of 2010 and the establishment of the Public-Private Partnership Node in the Health Department, the governance weaknesses in contract management, performance monitoring, and provider payment incentives limit their effectiveness as strategic purchasing mechanisms. These purchasing governance failures contribute to urban and tertiary care bias in resource allocation, perpetuating inequities between urban and rural populations despite evidence suggesting better performance from facilities operating under more strategic purchasing arrangements.

Sindh's public healthcare system lacks a well-defined health benefits package, creating significant ambiguity about population entitlements. While every resident is theoretically entitled to free public healthcare, there is no formal definition of included or excluded services, preventing effective accountability for service delivery. The absence of explicit entitlement definitions has allowed provider preferences and political considerations to drive service development rather than population needs. Recent initiatives to develop a Universal Health Coverage Benefit Package (UHC-BP) based on evidence represent a promising governance innovation that could transform financing arrangements by explicitly defining population entitlements and connecting them to resource requirements. The planned pilot implementation in the Tando Allah Yar district allows testing this approach before province-wide expansion, potentially addressing one of the most significant governance gaps in Sindh's health financing system.

Developing a comprehensive provincial health financing strategy emerges as the top priority recommendation to address the governance challenges identified in this landscape. These governance issues across revenue raising, pooling, purchasing, and benefits functions collectively create a fragmented financing system that requires a comprehensive health financing strategy. The strategy should establish a unified framework aligning revenue raising, pooling, purchasing, and benefits design under coherent governance arrangements guided by shared objectives. The strategy development process should be led by the Health Department in collaboration with key provincial departments, including Finance, Planning and Development, and Population Welfare, to ensure ownership and implementation feasibility, given their critical role in resource allocation decisions and service delivery. To support these efforts, the Health Department should establish a dedicated health financing unit to coordinate, implement, and monitor the strategy. The strategy should establish formal coordination mechanisms with clear mandates and specified decision-making authorities to address the significant governance gaps in horizontal coordination between departments and vertical coordination between federal and provincial levels. By developing this overarching framework, Sindh can overcome the fragmentation that undermines financing governance effectiveness and accelerate progress toward universal health coverage goals that remain elusive under current arrangements.

INTRODUCTION

Effective governance is the cornerstone of successful health financing systems in Sindh, directly influencing progress toward universal health coverage (UHC). Sound governance ensures that health financing functions operate equitably and efficiently, determining how resources are generated, pooled, and allocated across the province while protecting citizens from financial hardship (World Health Organization 2000). It involves the development and execution of policies for healthcare funding that align with broader health system goals and population needs, creating accountability for system performance through rules or outcome-based indicators (Greer, Wismar, and Figueras 2016; Holst 2017). The management and oversight of financing mechanisms directly impact service accessibility, affordability, and quality, with weak governance structures often undermining otherwise well-designed policies through inadequate coordination, limited transparency, or ineffective accountability (Fryatt, Bennett, and Soucat 2017). Even sophisticated financing arrangements may fail without proper governance (Kutzin, Witter, and Jowett 2017), leading to inefficiencies and inadequate financial protection for vulnerable populations across Sindh's 55.6 million residents. This landscape examines health financing governance in Sindh, identifying key challenges and opportunities for reform that can strengthen the provincial health system's performance beyond consideration of technical design alone (Siddiqi et al. 2009).

BACKGROUND

Sindh's unique demographic and socioeconomic profile shapes its health financing governance challenges and opportunities. With a population of approximately 55.6 million people (23.1% of Pakistan's total population), Sindh is the second-most populous province in the country (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics 2023). The province exhibits stark urban-rural disparities, with nearly 54% of its population concentrated in urban areas, primarily in Karachi, one of South Asia's largest metropolises (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics 2020). Socioeconomically, Sindh displays significant inequality, with 52.5% of its population classified as multi-dimensionally poor when measuring health, education, and living standards, despite the province's relative economic strength nationally (Haq et al. 2024). Sindh's economy contributes approximately 30% of Pakistan's gross domestic product (GDP), with strengths in manufacturing, services, and agriculture, providing a potentially stronger tax base than other provinces (World Bank 2018). These demographic and economic characteristics directly influence health needs and the fiscal capacity available for health financing governance within the province.

Health indicators in Sindh reveal gaps that reflect financing and broader governance challenges in the provincial health system. The maternal mortality ratio in Sindh stands at 224 per 100,000 live births, significantly higher than the national average of 186, indicating weaknesses in maternal health services despite the province's relatively strong urban health infrastructure (National Institute of Population Studies and ICF 2020). Only 70.2% of deliveries occur in institutional settings, with stark urban-rural disparities in access to skilled birth attendance that reflect inequitable resource distribution and service availability (Sindh Bureau of Statistics 2019). The province faces a high total fertility rate of 3.7 and a low contraceptive prevalence rate of 21.5%, reflecting limited access to and utilization of family planning services (Sindh Bureau of Statistics 2019). Childhood immunization coverage is 55%, below the national average of 66%, indicating inefficiencies in basic preventive service delivery (Pakistan Demographic and Health Survey 2017-18). These health outcomes directly connect to governance challenges in financing, resource allocation, and service delivery coordination, which this landscape will examine.

At the national level, Pakistan's health financing indicators consistently lag behind regional and global benchmarks, creating systemic challenges for provincial health systems, including Sindh. The World Health Organization's (WHO) Health Financing Progress Matrix (HFPM) assessment for 2023 revealed that Pakistan's service coverage index (SCI) for UHC is 45, significantly lower than the average score of 58 reported among lower-middle income countries.

Correspondingly, the prevalence of catastrophic health spending, calculated at 10% and 25% of household income thresholds, has consistently increased in Pakistan since 2007 (World Health Organization 2023). THE stands at approximately 3.4% of GDP, significantly below the 5% minimum recommended by WHO for countries aiming to achieve UHC (World Health Organization 2023).

Government health expenditure (see **Table 1**) accounts for only 0.8% of GDP and 4.6% of general government expenditure (GGE), well below the lower-middle income countries average of 2.6% of GDP and 8.7% of GGE, respectively. Current health expenditure per capita remains low at US\$43.1, compared to the lower-middle income country average of US\$157.3, limiting the scope and quality of the system's services (World Health Organization 2021). The inadequate public financing creates heavy reliance on private expenditure, which constitutes 60.7% of total health expenditure, with 97% coming from OOP household payments (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics 2024). This financing structure creates significant financial barriers to healthcare access and exposes households to catastrophic health expenditures, with approximately 4.4% of households experiencing health costs exceeding 10% of their total consumption (World Health Organization 2023).

Sindh's health financing environment reflects province-specific characteristics and broader national patterns. According to National Health Accounts (NHA) 2021-22, private sources constitute the majority (69.2%) of health expenditure in Sindh, with OOP payments accounting for 81% of private spending, creating significant financial barriers to healthcare access and equity challenges (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics 2024). Public funding contributes approximately 30.7% of total health expenditure, primarily from general taxation, with provincial allocations to health representing about 14.6% of total provincial government spending—higher than the national average but insufficient to meet population needs (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics 2024). Sindh's current health expenditure per capita stands at approximately US\$41.5 (adjusted for the fiscal year 2021-22), slightly below the national average despite the province's relative economic advantage (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics 2024). These financing patterns directly influence governance arrangements by shaping the pool of resources available for allocation and the mechanisms required for effective service delivery and financial protection.

The 18th Constitutional Amendment fundamentally transformed health financing governance by transferring primary responsibility to provinces. In 2010, this landmark legislation abolished the

Table 1. Health financing indicators in Pakistan

Indicator	Pakistan's Value for 2021	Income Group (Average)
Revenue Sources		
Domestic public (GGHE as % of THE)	29%	42.9%
Domestic private (private as % of THE)	60.7%	26.2%
External (external as % of THE)	10.3%	19.1%
Health Expenditure		
Budget priority for health (GGHE as % of GGE)	4.6%	8.7%
Public spending on health as % of GDP	0.8%	2.6%
Current health expenditure per capita (US\$)	\$43.1	\$157.3

Notes: THE = total health expenditures
 GGE = general government expenditures
 GGHE = general government health expenditures.

Source: WHO Health Financing Dashboard: Pakistan Profile 2021 (<https://www.who.int/teams/health-systems-governance-and-financing/health-financing/hfpm-background-indicators>)

concurrent legislative list (Government of Pakistan 2010) that had previously enabled federal involvement in health policy and financing, establishing provincial governments as the principal authorities for health sector governance (Nishtar 2011). Before devolution, the federal Ministry of Health¹ played a central role in health financing through national programs, donor coordination, and policy guidance, with provinces serving primarily as implementing agencies with limited policymaking authority (Khan 2019). The constitutional change required provinces to rapidly develop capacity for health policy analysis, strategic planning, and financial management functions previously coordinated at the federal level. While the federal government largely retained revenue collection, provinces assumed primary responsibility for pooling and purchasing functions (Nishtar 2011; Zaidi et al. 2019). This transformation represents one of the most significant governance reforms in Pakistan's history, with profound implications for how health financing decisions are made, implemented, and monitored throughout the system (Bossert and Mitchell 2011).

Multiple stakeholders influence health financing governance in Sindh, creating a complex landscape that requires effective coordination mechanisms (see Table 2). The Federal Ministry of Finance influences provincial fiscal space through the NFC award and transfer mechanisms. At the same time, the federal Ministry of Health provides technical guidance on health financing reforms. Provincial stakeholders include the Health Department, which sets policies for health financing functions, such as pooling through designing benefit packages and purchasing of health services and budget allocations; the Finance Department, which mobilizes and allocates funds; and specialized units, such as the Public-Private Partnership Node, which facilitates private sector engagement. Other key actors include the Sindh Healthcare Commission, which regulates public and private providers; the Sindh Revenue Board, which manages provincial taxation; and various development partners providing technical assistance. This multiplicity of stakeholders creates governance challenges in establishing clear accountability lines, coordinating policy decisions, and ensuring aligned implementation of health financing functions. The involvement of various actors with overlapping mandates often leads to fragmented decision-making and delays in the execution of health financing reforms. Effective governance requires formal coordination mechanisms that reduce fragmentation and enhance coherence across these diverse actors.

Table 2. Stakeholder and key functions in health financing

Stakeholder	Key Functions
Federal Government	
Ministry of Finance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensures the timely release of provincial funds. Ensures a feasible environment and technical guidance for the provinces when implementing tax and/or health financing reforms.
Ministry of National Health Services, Regulations and Coordination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provides technical assistance with respect to health financing reforms. Ensures the alignment of reforms with international standards/obligations.
Provincial Government	
Health Department	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sets policies, regulations, and budget allocations. Provides the legal and regulatory framework for health financing reforms. Develops health benefit packages. Sets standards and procedures that govern healthcare delivery. Improves governance and accountability in health financing mechanisms.
Director-General Health Services, Health Department	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensures the coordination between the provincial health department (policymakers) and its district counterparts (implementers, at large).
District Health Officers (DHOs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensures the effective and efficient implementation of health financing reforms, interventions, plans, etc.
Sindh Revenue Board	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensures effective tax collection if the Sindh government plans to implement pro-health taxes in the provinces.

¹ Officially the Ministry of National Health Services, Regulation and Coordination (MoNHSRC)

Finance Department	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobilizes funds. • Coordinates with the federal government to ensure the timely release of funds. • Extracts and analyzes budget expenditure trends across different entities within the health department. • Plays a role in financial management rules and regulations related to health financing.
Planning and Development Board	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leads the formulation and appraisal of the health sector's development budget. • Plays a central role in development sector financing and aligning investments with the health sector's strategic priorities. • Serves as the first point of contact for development partners and coordinates intersectoral development planning and implementation.
Public-Private Partnership Unit (PPP) (Finance Department)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appraises PPP projects. • Provides funds through a project support facility.
PPP Node (Health Department)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifies, analyzes, and ascertains the feasibility of PPP projects in the health sector. • Informs decision-making around strategic purchasing.
Sindh Public Procurement Regulatory Authority	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensures effective procurement in line with regulations.
Sindh Health Care Commission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensures the registration, licensing, and quality checks of the province's healthcare providers (both public and private).
Others	
Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensures awareness, publicity, and dissemination of information.
Academia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expands the knowledge base and generates evidence to bridge the policy-research gap, builds capacity for health financing, and acts as a knowledge repository.
Private Sector (healthcare providers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proactively engages with the PPP Node for effective, efficient, and sustainable delivery of healthcare services.
Development Partners/ Donors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides technical assistance to design, implement, monitor, and evaluate health financing reforms.

Source: Authors' Analysis

The administrative structure of Sindh's health system follows a complex, multi-tiered organization that influences financing flows and governance arrangements (see Figure 1).

The Health Department is divided into two main administrative streams at the provincial level: Health Services and Medical Education, each with distinct

leadership and reporting lines. The Health Services stream is led by the Director-General of Health Services, with various vertical programs and specialized units operating under this authority with varying degrees of financial autonomy. The centralized administration within Sindh's Health Department presents significant challenges to effective health service delivery, manifesting in highly centralized decision-making and a top-down relationship, lacking a shared goal across different levels. This disconnect between de jure decentralization and de facto centralized governance exemplifies the inefficiencies inherent in the current system, ultimately hindering

Figure 1. Hierarchy of administrative structures of Sindh's Health Department

Source: Authors' analysis of Sindh's Health Department website

the overall effectiveness of health service delivery in Sindh (Zaidi et al. 2019). These administrative arrangements directly shape health financing governance by determining decision-making authority, fund flow mechanisms, and accountability relationships.

In Sindh, the public sector healthcare delivery system follows the national standard, while the private sector dominates actual service provision. The Health Department and its Public-Private Partners are the principal healthcare providers in Sindh's public healthcare system. Primary health care (PHC) services are predominantly delivered by Peoples' Primary Healthcare Initiative (PPHI) Sindh,² while the Health Department manages the remaining PHC services, especially in Karachi. In Sindh, private providers dominate the provision of health services, with about 83% of the national population accessing the private sector for health services (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics 2024). This is supported by the fact that OOP expenditure in the private sector accounts for 81% (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics 2024). The Sindh Healthcare Commission's limited effectiveness compounds these issues, as it struggles to enforce standards and regulations that could safeguard patients and ensure equitable access to good-quality health care (Zaidi 2021).

PPHI Sindh exemplifies the Section 42 company model and plays a crucial role in primary healthcare delivery across the province. PPHI Sindh manages over half of the province's PHC facilities under a five-year, non-binding Memorandum of Understanding with the Health Department. It receives annual single-line transfers as a global budget from the government of Sindh and operates without being subject to the government's rigid rules for procurement and recruitment. Meanwhile, the Health Department manages the remaining PHC services, especially in Karachi.

METHODOLOGY

This paper employs a standard framework to evaluate Sindh's health financing system, focusing on governance around key health financing functions. The framework, adopted from Kutzin and others (Kutzin 2001; Kutzin et al. 2017) (see **Figure 2**. The WHO health financing framework), encompasses the core functions of health financing systems: revenue raising, pooling of funds, purchasing of services, and designing benefits to ultimately ensure the provision of services. Revenue collection

Figure 2. The WHO health financing framework

Source: Kutzin et al. 2017

² PPHI Sindh, formerly known as People's Primary Health care Initiative, is a not-for-profit entity registered under section 42 of The Companies Act 2017 (<https://pphisindh.org/home/about-us.php>).

secures funds from various sources, including households, businesses, and donors. Pooling accumulates these revenues to spread financial risk across population groups, ensuring no individual bears the entire healthcare cost burden. Purchasing involves using pooled funds to pay providers, ranging from passive disbursement to strategic approaches that optimize performance (World Health Organization 2000). The benefits design defines service packages, outlining population entitlements and obligations and ensuring awareness and alignment with provider payment mechanisms (Kutzin, Witter, and Jowett 2017). Each function requires effective governance arrangements to ensure transparency, accountability, and alignment with health system goals.

The WHO framework facilitates an in-depth examination of the complex interactions between the health financing system and the population. Governance is crucial for effective health financing, influencing the core pillars of revenue raising, pooling, purchasing, and benefits design. This governance framework encompasses administrative structures, stakeholder involvement in decision-making, and the legal environment surrounding health financing. It represents a set of actions designed to align key elements of the health financing system with defined policy objectives. Governance bodies employ various tools to achieve this alignment, including implementing regulatory frameworks, disseminating vital information, and establishing oversight arrangements for agencies within the health financing ecosystem. These actions ensure accountability and adherence to established standards. Beyond regulation, governance shapes the administrative landscape, orchestrates stakeholder involvement, and cultivates a conducive legal environment for health financing. It develops and updates frameworks supporting innovative financing mechanisms, protects healthcare consumers' rights, and promotes equitable access to services. Ultimately, governance of financing serves as the guiding force steering the health financing system toward efficiency, equity, and sustainability. Aligning core pillars creates a cohesive system that meets evolving healthcare needs while ensuring financial protection and optimal resource utilization.

The framework provides an organizing approach rather than a fixed set of evaluation criteria (see Figure 2. The WHO health financing framework). Rather than prescribing rigid benchmarks or performance indicators, it guides analysis by structuring thinking around key health financing functions: revenue raising, pooling, purchasing, and benefits design. Focusing on functions rather than specific financing models accommodates diverse country contexts while providing a common language for health financing analysis (Kutzin 2013). In applying this framework to Sindh, administrative structures, stakeholders' roles, legal frameworks, and coordination mechanisms were examined to assess how effectively they support sustainable health financing. The overview identifies opportunities to strengthen governance arrangements to improve performance and advance toward UHC goals. By providing evidence-based recommendations, this research aims to support policymakers in reforming Sindh's health financing amid such persistent challenges as high OOP spending, inadequate public investment, and inequitable resource distribution.

This analysis is based on an extensive review of publicly available documents and data sources. These include Sindh government documents such as the Rules of Business 1986, Public Procurement Rules 2010, PPP Act 2010, Delegation of Financial Powers and Financial Rules 2019, Public Financial Management (PFM) Handbook 2019, and Sindh Public Financial Administration Act of 2020. The Information Management Unit dashboard of the government's finance department provided data on financial flows and allocations. Information on the Health Department's governance arrangements and key functions was obtained from the department's website and the office of the Director-General of Health Services. By exploring the administrative structures, stakeholders' roles, legal frameworks, and coordination mechanisms that influence health financing functions, the study identifies key governance challenges and opportunities for reform. This analysis provides evidence-based insights to inform provincial policy development and implementation, supporting efforts to strengthen health financing arrangements and advance progress toward UHC in Sindh.

GOVERNANCE OF HEALTH FINANCING IN SINDH

HEALTH FINANCING LANDSCAPE

Sindh's health financing landscape is characterized by high private expenditure, limited public funding, and significant urban-rural disparities that hinder progress toward UHC. As noted in the Background section, private expenditures (69.2% of THE, of which 81% is OOP) dominate health financing in Sindh and place a substantial financial burden on households, creating significant barriers to healthcare access, particularly for lower-income populations (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics 2024). Public funding as a share of THE has shown minimal improvement over the past decade despite constitutional devolution and increased provincial fiscal authority. External funding from international donors and development partners provides a mere 0.1% of health expenditure in Sindh, significantly lower than in other provinces such as Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (8.7%) and Balochistan (5.2%), reflecting both donor priorities and provincial policy choices regarding external assistance (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics 2024). This financing structure perpetuates healthcare access and utilization inequities while exposing households to financial hardship when seeking care.

Health expenditure per capita in Sindh is below international benchmarks and estimates of basic healthcare cost requirements. Despite Sindh's position as one of Pakistan's wealthier provinces—generating approximately 30% of the national GDP—its health expenditure per capita (US\$41.5) remains slightly below the national average of US\$43.1 and significantly lower than the lower-middle income country average of US\$157.3 (World Health Organization 2021). This paradox of relatively strong economic performance coupled with inadequate health investment reflects governance challenges in resource mobilization and allocation rather than absolute resource constraints. A temporal analysis of health expenditure trends shows that public health spending as a percentage of Sindh's provincial budget has fluctuated between 10% and 14.6% over the past five years, demonstrating inconsistent prioritization despite the province's constitutional authority over health financing decisions (World Bank 2023). The World Bank's Public Expenditure Review for Sindh found that actual health expenditure frequently falls below budgeted amounts, with execution rates averaging 82% from 2018 to 2022, indicating challenges in budget implementation and financial management (World Bank 2023). These financing inadequacies contribute to persistent gaps in service availability and quality of services. Financial protection also remains weak, with high OOP costs deterring care-seeking and pushing low-income households into poverty due to health-related expenses. These gaps disproportionately affect rural and marginalized populations, exacerbating existing health inequities across the province.

Significant urban-rural disparities exist in health financing and expenditure patterns across Sindh, contributing to inequitable health outcomes and service access. Analysis of household survey data indicates that urban households in Sindh spend approximately 2.3 times more on healthcare in absolute terms than rural households, reflecting both higher service availability and greater capacity to pay in urban areas, particularly in Karachi (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics 2020). However, rural households face a heavier financial burden when measured as a percentage of household income, with health expenditures consuming an average of 8.2% of household income, compared to 5.6% in urban areas (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics 2020). This disproportionate burden occurs despite lower utilization rates in rural areas, indicating higher financial barriers to access. The public sector's tertiary healthcare caters to only 15% of Pakistan's population while accounting for around 85% of the country's healthcare spending (Islam 2002). The available financing primarily targets tertiary care, often neglecting primary and preventive healthcare services (Shaikh et al. 2013; Samnani et al. 2018; Ministry of National Health Services, Regulations and Coordination 2023). The concentration of tertiary health facilities in urban centres, particularly Karachi and Hyderabad, further skews resource allocation away from primary and secondary care services that would benefit rural populations. These distributional imbalances reflect governance failures in needs-based resource allocation and planning. Weak inter-district planning processes, limited use of equity-focused data in

budgeting, and inadequate rural representation in decision-making contribute to persistent rural-urban gaps in resource distribution and health indicators.

LEGAL ENVIRONMENT

The legal environment around financing in Sindh provides a robust foundation for enhancing financial management across sectors, including healthcare. These legal frameworks are designed to apply in general across all sectors of the Sindh government and are not specifically formulated for the health sector. Despite not being health-specific, these laws can significantly improve health financing by fostering strategic PPPs to optimize resources and expand healthcare access, ensuring transparent financial practices through adherence to Sindh Public Finance Administration directives, and facilitating cost-effective procurement of healthcare supplies via structured procurement committees. Effectively utilizing these legal tools within the health sector can improve service delivery, stronger governance structures, and sustainable health financing outcomes that better address the population's healthcare needs.

Sindh lacks a comprehensive health financing policy or strategy, creating a fragmented governance environment where financing decisions occur without a coherent guiding framework. Sindh has not established a dedicated policy framework to guide health financing decisions. The Sindh Health Sector Strategy 2012-2020 included broad references to health financing challenges but lacked specific mechanisms, targets, or implementation plans for addressing these issues (Zaidi 2012). This policy gap has resulted in ad hoc financing decisions driven by historical patterns, political considerations, and bureaucratic processes rather than strategic priorities or evidence-based allocation criteria. The absence of a formal health financing strategy also creates coordination challenges among various departments, agencies, and programs involved in health financing decisions, limiting Sindh's ability to develop coherent approaches to revenue raising, pooling, purchasing, and benefits design. This policy vacuum has contributed to inefficient resource allocation, fragmented financing streams, and weak accountability mechanisms despite constitutional authority for health financing reforms following devolution.

The PFM framework in Sindh provides procedural guidance for health financing but contains significant gaps in effectiveness, transparency, and strategic orientation. The Sindh Public Finance Administration Act of 2020 provides the legal foundation for budget formulation, execution, accounting, and reporting across all sectors, including health (Finance Department, Government of Sindh 2020). This legislation establishes formal processes for annual budget cycles, financial controls, and expenditure monitoring, creating the basic infrastructure for financial governance. The Sindh Delegation of Financial Powers Rules of 2019 specifies authorized spending levels for various administrative positions within the health system, from the provincial secretary to facility managers, defining decision-making authority for financial transactions. While these laws create procedural clarity, they emphasize compliance and control rather than strategic resource allocation or performance-based budgeting. The Public Procurement Regulatory Authority Act of 2010 governs procurement processes for health commodities and services but has faced implementation challenges, with audits revealing persistent irregularities in health procurement. Recent PFM reforms, including the introduction of a medium-term budgetary framework and program-based budgeting, aim to strengthen the strategic orientation of financial management but remain in the early implementation stages within the health sector.

The legal framework for PPPs in health financing demonstrates both the potential and limitations of Sindh's approach to innovative financing mechanisms. The Sindh PPP Act of 2010 establishes the legal basis for contracting arrangements between the provincial government and private entities for infrastructure development and service delivery in various sectors, including health. Building on this framework, the Health Department established a dedicated PPP Node to identify, develop, and manage partnership opportunities within the health sector, creating an institutional focal point for private sector engagement (Zaidi 2021). However, the legal framework emphasizes procedural aspects of partnership formation (see Figure 3) rather than strategic objectives, performance management, or accountability mechanisms (Khan and Pappas 2019). Evaluations of existing health PPPs have identified significant gaps between legal provisions and implementation reality, with weak contract management, limited performance monitoring, and inadequate dispute resolution mechanisms undermining their effectiveness (Zaidi 2021). These weaknesses hinder the ability to ensure value for money, equity, and efficiency in health service delivery—key health financing goals. As a result, PPPs often fail to deliver improved access, cost-effectiveness, or quality outcomes, ultimately constraining the effectiveness of innovative financing solutions intended to expand and strengthen the health system.

Figure 3. PPP processes in Sindh

Source: Authors' analysis of Sindh's PPP Act 2010

REVENUE COLLECTION

Sindh's revenue collection for health financing operates within a constitutionally established yet centralized fiscal architecture that significantly constrains provincial autonomy despite devolution.

The province's health financing relies heavily on federal transfers through the National Finance Commission (NFC) award, constituting approximately 82% of Sindh's overall revenue (World Bank 2017; Ahmed and Mahmood 2018). Although the 18th Amendment to the Constitution grants provinces constitutional authority over health, this authority is undermined by fiscal dependence on national resource allocations. Article 160 of the Constitution establishes the NFC as the framework for intergovernmental resource distribution, and the 7th NFC Award increased the provincial share of the federal divisible pool from 45% to 57.5% (see Figure 4) (Finance Division 2010).

Figure 4. Federal health financing resource distribution criteria and share among provinces

Source: Authors' Analysis of relevant sources

Under the weighted distribution formula—population (82%), poverty (10.3%), revenue generation (5%), and inverse population density (2.7%)—Sindh receives 24.6% of total provincial allocations, behind Punjab but ahead of other provinces (Finance Division 2010). Despite having the authority to expand its tax base, Sindh’s own-source revenues—generated through taxes on services, property, motor vehicles, and various fees—contribute merely 18% of its total revenue (World Bank 2017; Ahmed and Mahmood 2018). This mismatch between devolved authority and limited fiscal autonomy reflects a fundamental governance challenge: The provincial ability to pursue health financing reforms remains constrained by external fiscal decisions. Multiple resource flow mechanisms—including NFC shares, development program allocations, federal grants, and straight transfers—collectively determine the fiscal space available for health investments at the provincial level. However, with no guaranteed health allocation in the distribution formula at the provincial level, the health sector must compete with other provincial priorities for limited fiscal space, undermining predictability and sustainability in health investments (Zaidi et al. 2019).

Private funds constitute the primary revenue source for health funding in Sindh. A review of the last three NHAs indicates that around 65% to 69% of health spending is done by private sources, followed by 30% to 34% from public/government, and with minimal contribution from external funding (see Figure 5). OOP spending accounts for 80% to 81% of total private funds, followed by the local nongovernmental organizations' share of 18% to 19% and employee funds around 1%. This heavy reliance on OOP spending creates significant financial barriers for households and exacerbates inequities in healthcare access across the province.

Figure 5. Revenue source trends in Sindh

Source: Authors' analysis of NHA data from the Pakistan Bureau of Statistics

General government taxes are the second largest funding source, accounting for roughly one-third of total funding. The receipt of the public share of the budget in the health sector depends entirely on tax collection and federal receipts, specifically routed through the provincial consolidated fund. While general taxes are a necessary financing mechanism for health, in Pakistan, they are proving insufficient due to other competing priorities of the government. There are no earmarked taxes for the health sector. This lack of dedicated funding reduces predictability and stability in health financing, limits the government's ability to plan and invest in long-term health initiatives, and makes the sector more vulnerable to political shifts and fiscal shocks. Two additional mandatory financing mechanisms exist: social security is funded by contributions from private employers, and Zakat³ is deducted from private savings. Both funds are collected at the federal level, and neither is earmarked for health. Social security accounted for around 1.1% of Sindh's total health revenue from 2021 to 2022. Private health insurance plans are funded through contributions and are primarily located in major cities (Malik 2015). According to the Multiple Indicator Cluster Survey 2018-19 (Sindh Bureau of Statistics 2019), only 3.2% of Sindh's population is insured by any type of health insurance policy scheme. Instead, all the residents are entitled to free health services from all public sector health facilities. Sindh allocated about 12% of its fiscal year 2023-24 budget to the Health Department.

These governance weaknesses have resulted in persistent underfunding of the health sector. Public financing contributes only 30.7% of total health expenditure, significantly below regional benchmarks for countries at similar income levels. The dominance of OOP spending (55.4% of total health expenditure) reflects governance failure in developing adequate prepayment mechanisms, creating substantial financial barriers for households seeking care (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics 2024). Rural populations face a disproportionate burden, with health expenditures consuming 8.2% of household income, compared to 5.6% in urban areas despite lower utilization rates, indicating significant equity failures in revenue governance.

POOLING

Sindh's health financing system is characterized by a unique structure that hinges on a centralized public sector tax pool, which serves as the backbone of health financing in the province. While providing certain structural advantages, this system also presents challenges that must be carefully navigated to ensure optimal health outcomes. The dominant source of government revenue in Sindh is general taxation, which is collected at the federal level and subsequently allocated to provinces. Afterwards, the funds are further distributed at the provincial level to various ministries, including health. This centralized approach to health financing allows for a more unified and potentially equitable method of allocating resources across the public sector. Sindh reduces the complexity and inefficiency of fragmented health financing systems by concentrating resources in a single, dominant tax pool.

However, this reliance on federal tax-based allocations introduces its complications. The distribution of funds from the federal level is not always aligned with the specific needs of the province, and the lack of autonomy in revenue generation limits the flexibility of the provincial government in addressing emerging health priorities. Nonetheless, the tax pool's centralization can also be advantageous for Sindh. It simplifies the flow of funds, reduces administrative overhead, and enables a more strategic deployment of resources by directly funding public sector services or purchasing services from the private sector to meet the population's health needs.

Despite the strengths of Sindh's centralized pool, the system faces significant challenges. The most pressing issues do not stem from the presence of smaller, fragmented pools, such as those

³ Zakat is a mandatory charitable contribution required from financially able Muslims, typically calculated as 2.5% of one's annual savings and wealth.

dedicated to provincial secretariat employees, autonomous organizations, social security institutions, and voluntary health insurance schemes. While serving specific sub-populations, these pools are relatively small and typical of the formal sector in many settings across countries.⁴ The real challenge lies in the province's ability to enhance its revenue-raising capacity, ensuring sufficient resources are consistently channelled into the dominant tax pool. Without a robust mechanism for increasing revenue, the pool remains vulnerable to external financial pressures and may struggle to meet the growing health needs of the population. Additionally, the absence of a clearly defined and transparent criterion for allocating funds for the health sector within the province is a critical weakness that exacerbates inefficiencies and deepens inequities within the system. The current allocation process is often opaque, leading to potential mismatches between resource distribution and actual health needs. This lack of clarity hinders the province's ability to optimize spending and prioritize investments in areas that would yield the greatest impact, such as investments in PHC.

PURCHASING

The governance of resource allocation to providers remains predominantly passive in Sindh, reflecting limited institutional capacity and weak accountability mechanisms required for strategic resource allocation. The Health Department's allocation strategy relies heavily on historical budgeting patterns rather than structured, needs-based approaches or performance-linked criteria. Budget ceilings for health facilities are often rolled over annually without systematically reassessing service demand, population needs, or provider performance (Malik 2015). For example, primary healthcare centres in low-utilization areas frequently receive similar allocations year after year, regardless of community health indicators or staffing requirements. Moreover, allocations are typically input-based rather than linked to outputs or outcomes. This approach usually leads to disparities in resource distribution between urban and rural areas, with better-resourced facilities in urban centres receiving disproportionately higher funding than underfunded rural facilities. As a result, passive purchasing practices contribute to significant disparities in service availability and quality across different regions of Sindh.

The Health Department of Sindh serves as the primary purchaser of health services, utilizing both public sector facilities and PPPs. The purchasing mechanism in Sindh's health sector allocates funds to service providers, influencing service accessibility and quality across urban and rural regions. The budget allocation for health services, particularly in the current and development budgets, outlines the financial resources earmarked for health services. The Health Department usually allocates the budget for public tertiary and secondary care facilities in item-wise disaggregation that can be visualized at the respective facility level. These facilities benefit from the purchasing component, which directs resources toward enhancing service delivery capacities at these levels. For primary healthcare, the Health Department earmarks budget resources for Basic Health Units, Rural Health Centres, Mother and Child Health Centres, Dispensaries, and vertical programs (Malik et al. 2017). However, the PHC budget is allocated globally and can only be visualized and tracked at the level of the respective District Health Officer (DHO) and above.

Furthermore, within the purchasing framework, a significant portion of the health budget is allocated as single-line grants to various healthcare agencies. These include public sector autonomous hospitals/institutions, private sector hospitals, and private management agencies that manage public sector staff and facilities on behalf of the government. As detailed in [Annex I](#), for the fiscal year 2023-24, these grants account for approximately 41.7% of the total health sector budget, or PKR 89.540 billion out of PKR 214.5 billion. This allocation method aims to streamline financial flows and empower health facilities to manage their operational needs efficiently. However, the absence of the PPP Node's oversight and consideration of explicit performance-based criteria in this

⁴ The Multiple Indicator Cluster Survey found that only 3.2% of Sindh's population is covered by any type of health insurance.

category of budget allocation poses challenges, limiting the system's ability to adapt to emerging health crises or adjust resource distribution based on evolving healthcare demands. As a result, while the purchasing component ensures the flow of funds to health facilities, there is a recognized need for more flexible and responsive budgetary mechanisms to better address healthcare challenges and improve health outcomes in Sindh.

The Health Department's two primary outsourcing approaches lack crucial elements of performance management. The first approach involves contracting out PHC facilities to the PPHI Sindh, while the second outsources secondary care facilities to private partners. PPHI Sindh manages the majority of PHC facilities—1,297 out of 2,588⁵—under a non-binding Memorandum of Understanding renewed every five years. However, both outsourcing arrangements lack crucial performance management components such as clear objectives, performance checks, provider-purchaser risk-sharing mechanisms, and provider-payment influence mechanisms. These gaps weaken accountability for service quality and create little incentive for providers to improve performance or respond to community health needs. Resource use remains inefficient, without formal mechanisms to align payments with outcomes, and service delivery improvements are inconsistent. Additionally, financial allocations to the PPHI-managed PHC facilities are routed through the DHO concerned, leading to duplication of resources between PPHI and the Health Department. There has been no comprehensive evaluation of the impact of outsourcing on health service delivery in Sindh. A case study observed that outsourcing PHC facilities can significantly improve service quality and strengthen health systems by addressing government capacity limitations (Tanzil et al. 2014). Further, an independent analysis of health facility service readiness in Sindh found that outsourced facilities outperformed government-managed non-contract facilities across all quality dimensions (Zaidi 2021). However, the government lacks a system to regularly review the performance of outsourced facilities in Sindh, limiting its ability to ensure value for money and sustained improvements in healthcare.

The absence of a comprehensive system for performance management significantly undermines the potential benefits of Sindh's purchasing approaches. Despite some positive evaluations of outsourced facilities showing improved service quality and strengthening health systems (Tanzil et al. 2014), the government lacks a system to regularly review performance across all purchasing mechanisms. The PPP Node's capacity constraints include a lack of dedicated technical specialists for complex contract management and monitoring (Khan, Rai, and Engels 2024). Performance monitoring across all purchasing mechanisms relies largely on the provider's self-reported data, with limited independent verification or systematic evaluation of outcomes. This systematic gap in the performance monitoring framework represents a critical weakness in Sindh's purchasing arrangements, limiting the government's ability to ensure value for money and quality service delivery despite substantial financial investments through diverse purchasing mechanisms.

BENEFITS PACKAGE

The public healthcare system in Sindh lacks a well-defined health benefits package (HBP), leading to ambiguity about the scope of free healthcare services available to residents. Although every resident is entitled to free public healthcare, there is no formal list of health services that are either included ("positive list") or excluded ("negative list") from coverage. Implementing an explicit HBP would help manage expectations, streamline service delivery, and assist in budget allocation. In its absence, the growth of services offered in the public health system has been haphazard and lacks an objective basis. Service provision is often heavily influenced by provider preferences rather than population health needs. Consequently, public spending has become concentrated in tertiary care and urban areas. This has led to disparities in healthcare access and outcomes, particularly for rural

⁵ Director-General Health Services presentation, "Sindh Health Department Overview," August 2023, Karachi, Pakistan

and underserved populations (Malik 2015), and a lack of clear guidelines for providing free public services, resulting in confusion among healthcare providers and residents regarding their entitlements. Additionally, the absence of explicit entitlement definitions weakens accountability mechanisms across all financing functions. For example, performance cannot be measured against clear service obligations, and purchasing arrangements lack connection to defined benefit deliverables. As a result, efforts to improve healthcare equity and accessibility have been hindered.

To address this gap, the Sindh government is working on a Universal Health Coverage Benefit Package (UHC-BP) to define the essential health services accessible to all residents. This initiative aligns with Pakistan's commitment to UHC as outlined in the National Health Action Plan (2019-23) and Sustainable Development Goal 3. The UHC-BP is based on evidence from Disease Control Priorities 3, an international publication guiding cost-effective health interventions. In 2020, a costed Essential Package of Health Services (EPHS) was developed nationally, prioritizing interventions at various healthcare levels. In 2021, Sindh's Health Department tailored the national EPHS to fit the local context, focusing on PHC services to reduce OOP spending.

The piloting of the UHC-BP in Sindh marks a critical step toward operationalizing health financing reforms through evidence-based service delivery models. The province-specific UHC-BP is currently being piloted in Tando Allah Yar, a small rural district, through a collaborative process involving various stakeholders. The pilot aims to demonstrate how clearly defined service entitlements can enhance efficiency, equity, and financial protection in service delivery when linked to resource allocations. Expected outcomes include improved service readiness, reduced patient costs, and better alignment between health financing and service delivery. The results from this pilot will inform the refinement of the benefit package, support adjustments to financing mechanisms, and serve as an evidence base for scaling up the initiative across Sindh. However, successful scale-up will depend on sustained political commitment, enhanced technical capacity, and increased financial resources (Alwan et al. 2023).

CROSS-CUTTING GOVERNANCE ISSUES

Examining governance across health financing functions reveals five interconnected challenges that require integrated responses:

1. **Strategic direction and policy coherence:** Sindh operates without a comprehensive health financing strategy to guide decision-making across functions, creating a fragmented governance landscape that undermines system performance. This policy vacuum has resulted in ad hoc financing decisions driven more by historical patterns and political considerations than strategic priorities or evidence-based allocation criteria.
2. **Institutional coordination and capacity:** Sindh faces multidimensional coordination challenges that undermine health financing governance. Horizontally, provincial entities (Health, Finance, Planning and Development, and specialized agencies) operate in silos with limited strategic collaboration beyond procedural budget interactions. Vertically, coordination weaknesses persist between federal, provincial, and district levels despite constitutional devolution, creating misalignments in policy and implementation. The integration of core financing functions remains fragmented across departments, resulting in disconnects between revenue decisions, pooling arrangements, purchasing activities, and definitions of benefits. These coordination failures are compounded by severe technical capacity limitations, with key personnel lacking specialized training in health economics and financial management required for effective system governance.
3. **Geographic and socioeconomic equity:** Urban-rural disparities persist in resource allocation and financial protection, reflecting governance failures in needs-based distribution. These inequities manifest across all financing functions, with resource allocation, service availability, and financial protection disproportionately disadvantaging rural populations despite their greater health needs.

4. **Implementation and accountability:** Fund flow mechanisms create challenges for effective service delivery due to procedural complexities and timing misalignments. Decision-making authorities remain centralized at the provincial level despite district responsibilities for service delivery. The absence of explicit HBP and performance monitoring systems further weakens accountability across the financing system.
5. **Financial mechanisms:** PFM systems significantly influence health financing effectiveness through budget processes that remain largely disconnected from health outcomes. These systems emphasize compliance and control rather than strategic resource allocation or performance-based budgeting, creating rigidities in fund flows that impact service delivery.

The matrix (Table 3) highlights how governance challenges shape each core function of Sindh’s health financing system: revenue raising, pooling, purchasing, and benefits design. It connects the dots, showing how a lack of strategic direction, weak coordination, and rigid financial mechanisms cut across functions and limit system performance. For example, financing remains fragmented and reactive without a clear revenue strategy or defined entitlements. Readers can use this matrix as a quick reference tool to understand where governance breakdowns occur and how they ripple through the system. It points to practical entry points for reform, helping decision-makers target governance improvements that will strengthen financing overall.

Table 3. Relationship between governance challenges and financing functions

Governance Challenge	Revenue Raising	Pooling	Purchasing	Benefits Design
Strategic direction and policy coherence	No dedicated revenue strategy; ad hoc decisions	Fragmented pools without coordination	Passive allocation without a strategic vision	Undefined population entitlements
Institutional coordination and capacity	Limited provincial authority despite constitutional mandate	Weak mechanisms for redistribution	Underdeveloped contract management capacity	Insufficient technical expertise for package development
Geographic and socioeconomic equity	Higher OOP burden for rural households	Urban bias in resource distribution	Provider payments not adjusted for geographic needs	Service availability gaps in rural areas
Implementation and accountability	Budget execution delays affect service delivery	Opaque allocation criteria	Limited performance monitoring	Ambiguous service obligations
Financial mechanisms	Rigid budget structures limit innovation	Line-item controls restrict flexibility	Input-based payments without outcome focus	Unfunded mandates without resource alignment

These interconnected challenges require coordinated governance reforms across all health financing functions. The UHC-BP initiative, recent PFM reforms, and Sindh’s economic capacity provide promising foundations for addressing these challenges through a comprehensive provincial health financing strategy that establishes coherent governance arrangements guided by clear objectives and aligned implementation mechanisms. By strengthening institutional capacity and technical design across financing functions, Sindh can establish the governance foundations needed for more equitable, efficient, and responsive health financing arrangements that advance population health and financial protection throughout the province.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Sindh requires a comprehensive approach to health financing governance reform that addresses fundamental challenges across all financing functions. This landscape has identified five interconnected governance challenges that collectively constrain the province’s progress toward

UHC. Addressing these challenges requires coordinated interventions that strengthen governance arrangements for revenue raising, pooling, purchasing, and benefits design rather than isolated reforms in specific components. The following recommendations provide a strategic framework for governance reform based on the provincial context, institutional realities, and specific challenges identified in this overview. These recommendations must build on existing provincial initiatives while addressing the systemic governance weaknesses that currently undermine health financing effectiveness. Implementation should follow a phased approach that recognizes capacity constraints while establishing the foundation for sustainable governance improvements across the health financing system.

STRATEGIC DIRECTION AND POLICY COHERENCE

Sindh's highest priority should be developing a comprehensive provincial health financing strategy to address the policy fragmentation identified in this landscape. The absence of a coherent policy framework has resulted in disconnected approaches to financing functions, with decisions driven more by historical patterns and bureaucratic processes than strategic priorities or evidence-based criteria (Malik 2015). A provincial strategy would establish a unified framework to align revenue raising, pooling, purchasing, and benefits design under coherent governance arrangements guided by shared objectives (Kutzin et al. 2017). This strategy should harmonize with the National Health Financing Framework developed by the federal government while customizing approaches to Sindh's unique demographic profile, urban-rural disparities, and administrative context (Ministry of National Health Services, Regulations and Coordination 2023). Recent governance innovations, particularly the UHC-BP initiative, provide valuable foundations that can be expanded province-wide through systematic strategy development and implementation. The strategy development process should follow the key steps outlined in **Figure 6**, ensuring comprehensive stakeholder engagement, rigorous situation analysis, and systematic assessment of policy options to build provincial ownership.

Figure 6. Key steps for developing a health financing strategy

Source: Adapted from Kutzin et al. 2017

The health financing strategy should articulate clear governance objectives linked to UHC goals with explicit performance targets. Governance objectives should include enhancing policy coherence across financing functions, strengthening institutional coordination and capacity, improving geographic equity in resource allocation, establishing robust accountability mechanisms, and aligning financial systems with health outcomes (World Health Organization 2021). The strategy should establish measurable performance targets for each objective, creating a framework for monitoring governance improvements rather than focusing solely on technical design elements. These targets should address both process indicators (e.g., the establishment of coordination

mechanisms) and outcome indicators (e.g., reduction in urban-rural disparities in financing) to ensure a comprehensive assessment of governance performance. Quantitative and qualitative indicators should be balanced to capture different dimensions of governance effectiveness, recognizing that some improvements are not easily quantifiable. Regular reporting on these indicators should be institutionalized through formal feedback mechanisms that inform ongoing governance adjustments.

Guiding principles should be established for each health financing function to ensure strategic alignment across governance arrangements. Revenue-raising principles should emphasize increased reliance on public/compulsory funding sources, improved predictability of funding levels, and greater stability in fund flows throughout the fiscal year (Kutzin, Witter, and Jowett 2017). Pooling should focus on redistributing available prepaid funds, enabling complementarity between funding sources, and reducing fragmentation to simplify financial flows. Purchasing principles should promote allocation based on population health needs and provider performance, moving away from rigid line-item budgets and avoiding open-ended provider payment arrangements. Benefits design should emphasize raising public awareness of entitlements and obligations while aligning promised benefits with provider payment methods. These principles, summarized in **Table 4**, provide a coherent framework for governance decisions across financing functions while establishing clear criteria against which reforms can be evaluated.

Table 4. Guiding principles and strategic areas for a health financing strategy

Strategic Area	Guiding Principles
Revenue raising	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Move toward a predominant reliance on public/compulsory funding sources (i.e., some form of taxation). • Emphasize public/compulsory funding (e.g., taxation). • Improve predictability of funding levels over time. • Improve stability (e.g., regular budget execution) in the flow of funds throughout the year.
Pooling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve the ability to redistribute available prepaid funds. • Enable clear complementarity between funding sources. • Reduce fragmentation, duplication, and overlap to simplify financial flows.
Purchasing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allocate funding to providers based on population health needs, provider performance, or both (strategic purchasing). • Move away from rigid budgets or unmanaged fee-for-service reimbursement. • Create a unified data platform for patient activity across multiple health financing and coverage schemes. • Avoid open-ended provider payment arrangements.
Benefit designs, rationing, the basis for entitlement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raise public awareness of entitlements and obligations (e.g., who is entitled to what services and what payment is expected at the point of usage). • Align promised benefits with provider payment methods.

Source: Adapted from Kutzin et al. 2017

INSTITUTIONAL COORDINATION AND CAPACITY

Sindh should establish formal institutional mechanisms for horizontal, vertical, and functional coordination of health financing governance. Horizontal coordination requires creating a high-level inter-departmental body focused on health financing policy. This body should bring together key provincial entities (Health, Finance, Planning and Development) and specialized agencies to enable strategic collaboration beyond procedural budget interactions (Zaidi 2021). Vertical coordination demands structured mechanisms between federal, provincial, and district levels to address misalignments in policy and implementation that persist despite constitutional devolution (Zaidi et al. 2019). Functional coordination requires institutional arrangements that connect governance decisions across financing functions and address the current fragmentation between revenue, pooling, purchasing, and benefits governance. These coordination mechanisms should be formalized

through clear mandates, regular meeting schedules, and specified decision-making authorities rather than ad hoc arrangements that lack continuity and effectiveness (Martinez et al. 2017). Regular performance assessments of these mechanisms should be conducted to identify and address coordination gaps as they emerge.

Creating a dedicated health financing unit within the Health Department would significantly strengthen institutional capacity for governance across financing functions. The current distribution of financial management responsibilities across multiple units—including the administration wing, planning section, budget cell, and vertical program offices—creates fragmentation and coordination challenges that undermine governance effectiveness (World Bank 2017). A specialized health financing unit would provide a focal point for policy development, technical analysis, implementation oversight, and monitoring across financing functions. This unit should have clearly defined responsibilities for developing financing policies, coordinating with other departments and levels of government, managing technical assistance, and building system-wide capacity for health financing governance. Staff should include professionals with specialized expertise in health economics, financial management, strategic purchasing, and performance monitoring to address this landscape's significant technical capacity gaps. Adequate resources should be allocated to ensure this unit can effectively fulfil its governance functions while developing long-term institutional capabilities.

A comprehensive capacity development plan should address the technical and institutional gaps constraining health financing governance effectiveness. Technical capacity development should focus on building specialized skills in health economics, financial management, strategic purchasing, and performance monitoring across key positions within provincial and district health authorities (Khan 2020). This should include formal training programs and ongoing mentoring arrangements that translate knowledge into practical application within specific institutional contexts. Institutional capacity development should strengthen organizational structures, information systems, decision-making processes, and accountability mechanisms that enable effective governance implementation. The capacity development plan should specify priority areas, target positions, development approaches, resource requirements, and performance indicators to ensure systematic rather than ad hoc capacity building. Special attention should be given to district-level financial management capacity, addressing the disconnect between service delivery responsibilities and limited financial authority identified in this overview (Zaidi et al. 2019).

GEOGRAPHIC AND SOCIOECONOMIC EQUITY

Transparent, needs-based resource allocation mechanisms must be established to address the significant geographic inequities in health financing documented throughout Sindh. Current allocation patterns show troubling urban-rural disparities, with rural households facing a heavier financial burden, as health expenditures consume an average of 8.2% of household income compared to 5.6% in urban areas (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics 2020). To guide district distribution decisions, the health financing strategy should establish explicit resource allocation formulas incorporating population health needs, geographic access barriers, socioeconomic status, and service availability (World Bank 2023). These formulas should be developed through inclusive processes that engage technical experts and district representatives to ensure methodological rigour and political acceptability. Allocation decisions should be transparent, with clear documentation of criteria, data sources, and calculation methods to enable accountability and reduce political influence in distribution patterns. Regular equity assessments should be conducted to evaluate the impact of these allocation mechanisms and identify areas requiring adjustment to address persistent disparities.

Pooling arrangements should be designed to redistribute resources across geographic and socioeconomic groups as a core governance objective. The centralized tax pool in Sindh provides a potential foundation for equitable redistribution but requires explicit governance mechanisms to

realize this potential (Kutzin et al. 2017). Pooling governance should establish redistribution formulas that channel resources from wealthier urban to underserved rural areas through transparent criteria that advance geographic justice as a core objective. Risk adjustment mechanisms should be incorporated to account for population health needs, ensuring that allocations reflect actual requirements rather than historical patterns or political influence (World Health Organization 2023). Regional health accounts should be developed to track the flow of resources across geographic areas, providing the information base for equity-focused governance decisions. These arrangements should be progressively strengthened as data systems and governance capacity develop, moving toward more sophisticated needs-based resource allocation over time.

Purchasing mechanisms should incorporate geographic equity considerations through provider payment systems that incentivize service delivery in underserved areas. Current purchasing arrangements perpetuate urban bias through predominantly passive approaches that fail to address geographic disparities in service availability and quality (Malik 2015). Provider payment systems should incorporate geographic adjustment factors that provide higher reimbursement rates for services delivered in underserved areas, creating financial incentives to address supply-side constraints in rural districts. Performance-based components should include explicit equity indicators with financial rewards to reduce geographic disparities in service utilization and outcomes. Contract arrangements with private providers should include specific service obligations in underserved areas, linking payment to geographic equity objectives rather than market-driven service patterns. These equity-focused purchasing reforms should be implemented through a phased approach that starts with priority interventions and expands based on implementation experience.

IMPLEMENTATION AND ACCOUNTABILITY

The UHC-BP initiative should be expanded province-wide as a governance mechanism for connecting financing arrangements to explicit population entitlements. The current absence of defined benefits creates significant accountability challenges across financing functions, as service obligations remain ambiguous and performance cannot be measured against clear entitlement standards (Malik 2015). The UHC-BP pilot in Tando Allah Yar provides a valuable foundation for expanding explicit entitlements throughout the province, establishing clear accountability for service delivery while connecting benefits to resource requirements (Alwan et al. 2023). Governance arrangements for benefits package management should be institutionalized, potentially through a dedicated unit responsible for defining, updating, and monitoring the implementation of explicit entitlements across the province. Special attention should be paid to ensuring that benefit definitions align with available financing, avoiding unfunded mandates undermining implementation feasibility. Public information campaigns should raise awareness of defined entitlements and service access points, enabling community-based accountability mechanisms that complement formal governance arrangements.

Implementation governance should be strengthened through reformed fund flow mechanisms that address delays and complexities undermining service delivery. Present fund flow arrangements create significant challenges through procedural complexities, limited flexibility, and timing misalignments that delay resource availability at service points (World Bank 2017). Governance reforms should streamline release procedures to ensure timely availability of funds throughout the fiscal year, particularly for frontline facilities that lack alternative financing sources. Flexibility mechanisms should be incorporated to allow managers to reallocate resources based on local needs while maintaining appropriate accountability safeguards. Fund flow governance should incorporate performance elements that link timely and predictable financing to service delivery indicators, creating incentives for system improvement beyond procedural compliance. Regular reviews of fund flow effectiveness should be institutionalized, systematically identifying bottlenecks

and implementation barriers that require governance adjustments to ensure that resources reach service delivery points when needed.

Accountability mechanisms should be significantly strengthened through performance monitoring systems linked to explicit governance objectives across financing functions. Current accountability relationships focus predominantly on procedural compliance rather than performance achievement, limiting incentives for system improvement (Khan 2020). Governance arrangements should establish clear performance expectations for key actors across financing functions, moving beyond input monitoring to track outputs, outcomes, and impacts of financing decisions. Regular performance reviews should be institutionalized at provincial and district levels, providing structured opportunities to assess progress against defined objectives and to identify areas requiring governance adjustments. Public reporting on key performance indicators should be established, enhancing transparency and enabling citizen engagement in accountability processes beyond formal governmental mechanisms. Information systems should be strengthened to provide timely, reliable data for performance assessment, addressing the significant gaps in current monitoring capabilities that undermine accountability effectiveness.

FINANCIAL MECHANISMS AND PFM

Health financing governance should be integrated with broader PFM reforms to enhance strategic orientation and performance focus. Current PFM systems emphasize compliance and control rather than strategic resource allocation or performance-based budgeting, creating disconnects between financing policies and budget processes (Finance Department, Government of Sindh 2020). Governance arrangements should explicitly align with recent PFM innovations undertaken in Sindh, including the medium-term budgetary framework and program-based budgeting, leveraging these reforms to enhance the strategic orientation of health budget processes (World Bank 2023). This alignment should be formalized through joint planning processes between the Health and Finance departments, ensuring that budget frameworks and allocation decisions reflect health financing objectives. Implementation guidelines should be developed to operationalize these alignments, providing clear directions to provincial and district-level officials responsible for financial management. Regular joint reviews between health and finance authorities should assess the effectiveness of these integrated governance arrangements, identifying areas requiring adjustment to strengthen alignment between financing policies and budget processes.

Provider payment systems should transition toward more strategic approaches that link allocation decisions to defined performance criteria aligned with system objectives. Current payment mechanisms predominantly follow passive approaches that perpetuate historical patterns rather than incentivizing performance or responding to population needs (Malik 2015). Governance arrangements for strategic purchasing should specify institutional responsibilities for contract management, performance monitoring, and payment administration, addressing significant capacity gaps in these areas. These arrangements should establish clear criteria for performance assessment, linking provider payment to defined indicators that reflect service delivery and health outcome objectives. Implementation should follow a phased approach that begins with priority interventions and providers where capacity already exists, gradually expanding to broader applications as governance systems strengthen. Regular assessment of payment system effectiveness should be institutionalized, with governance mechanisms adjusted based on implementation experience and emerging evidence about performance impacts.

Financial transparency and citizen engagement in health financing governance should be significantly enhanced through public information mechanisms. Current financing decisions occur with limited public visibility or engagement, constraining accountability beyond formal governmental structures (Zaidi 2021). Governance arrangements should establish regular public reporting on health financing decisions, resource allocations, and performance outcomes in formats accessible to diverse stakeholders, including community representatives. Structured opportunities

for citizen input should be incorporated into financing governance, particularly around resource allocation decisions and benefits package definitions that directly impact population access. Digital platforms should be leveraged to enhance information accessibility while reducing costs associated with traditional dissemination methods. Financial literacy programs should be developed for community representatives and civil society organizations, enhancing their capacity to effectively engage with financing governance processes. These transparency mechanisms should be progressively strengthened based on implementation experience and stakeholder feedback.

IMPLEMENTATION CONSIDERATIONS

Implementation of these governance reforms should follow a phased approach that recognizes capacity constraints while establishing the foundation for sustained improvement. The first phase should focus on developing a comprehensive health financing strategy, establishing a health financing unit with strengthened coordination mechanisms, and expanding the UHC-BP pilot to additional districts. The second phase should strengthen resource allocation formulas, initiate strategic purchasing reforms, and align PFM systems with health financing objectives. The third phase should focus on consolidating reforms, institutionalizing performance monitoring, and refining governance arrangements based on implementation experience. This phased approach (see [Table 5](#)) recognizes that governance reform is an iterative process requiring progressive strengthening rather than one-time interventions. Through implementation, political economy factors should be carefully managed by building coalitions for reform, demonstrating early successes, and addressing legitimate concerns of stakeholders whose interests may be affected by governance changes. Regular assessment of implementation progress should guide adjustments to the reform sequence and pace, ensuring governance improvements remain responsive to emerging challenges and opportunities within Sindh's health financing system.

Table 5. Health financing governance challenges and recommendations matrix

Governance Challenges	Recommendations				
	Develop a Health Financing Strategy	Establish Coordination Mechanisms	Create Equitable Resource Allocation	Implement UHC-BP Initiative	Build Technical Capacity
Strategic direction and policy coherence	PRIMARY	Secondary	Minor	Secondary	Minor
Institutional coordination & capacity	Secondary	PRIMARY	Minor	Secondary	PRIMARY
Geographic and socioeconomic equity	Secondary	Minor	PRIMARY	Secondary	Minor
Implementation and accountability	Secondary	Secondary	Secondary	PRIMARY	Secondary
Financial mechanisms and PFM	Secondary	Minor	Secondary	Secondary	PRIMARY

Note: "PRIMARY" indicates recommendations with major impact on addressing specific challenges; "Secondary" indicates moderate impact; "Minor" indicates limited but relevant impact.

While this landscape offers valuable insights into health financing governance in Sindh, it has important limitations. The analysis draws exclusively from secondary data sources, which may not fully reflect current on-the-ground realities. The absence of **primary** data from key stakeholders limits the diversity and depth of perspectives included, potentially affecting the comprehensiveness of the findings and recommendations. To build on this work, future research should incorporate primary data collection, engaging stakeholders directly to capture more nuanced insights. Further studies should also examine the implementation of strategic purchasing and the effectiveness of pooling arrangements, critical areas identified in this overview that warrant deeper exploration.

CONCLUSION

Effective governance represents the foundation of health financing performance in Sindh, requiring immediate and sustained reforms to achieve universal health coverage. This landscape has identified significant governance challenges across all health financing functions that collectively constrain equitable resource allocation and financial protection. Strengthening governance arrangements—rather than merely adjusting technical design elements—offers the most promising pathway for transformative improvement. While Sindh faces resource constraints, governance weaknesses in strategic direction, institutional coordination, equity mechanisms, accountability systems, and financial management present more fundamental barriers to progress. Provincial leadership must recognize that constitutional devolution has transferred authority without corresponding governance capacity, creating a critical disconnect between formal responsibility and implementation capability that requires deliberate attention.

Developing a comprehensive health financing strategy is the first step in addressing the governance fragmentation identified throughout this landscape. This strategy should establish coherent governance arrangements across financing functions through participatory processes that engage key stakeholders in design and implementation. Initial governance reforms should focus on establishing a health financing unit and strengthening coordination mechanisms between departments and levels of government, developing transparent resource allocation formulas, and expanding the UHC-BP initiative to strengthen accountability through explicit entitlements. These foundational reforms create the governance infrastructure needed for more sophisticated financing arrangements while addressing immediate equity and implementation challenges. Provincial leadership must extend political commitment beyond strategy development to sustained implementation support through changing administrative and political cycles.

To turn analysis into action, Sindh must translate governance insights into a concrete reform agenda. To initiate this process, Sindh’s Health Department should convene a high-level forum—including representatives from Health, Finance, Planning and Development, and other key stakeholders—to lead the development of the provincial health financing strategy. This forum should be empowered to define priorities, coordinate reform efforts, and guide implementation.

Governance reforms offer transformative potential for Sindh's health system despite implementation challenges in the provincial context. By strengthening governance arrangements across financing functions, Sindh can establish more equitable, efficient, and responsive mechanisms that significantly improve population health outcomes and financial protection. Recent initiatives—particularly the UHC-BP pilot and public financial management reforms—provide valuable foundations for broader governance improvements when implemented within a coherent strategic framework. Provincial leadership has the constitutional authority, institutional framework, and reform opportunities needed to strengthen health financing governance despite resource constraints and capacity limitations. By establishing clear governance priorities and implementation pathways, Sindh can accelerate progress toward universal health coverage goals that remain elusive under current arrangements.

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ANNEX I: SINGLE-LINE GRANTS IN FISCAL YEAR 2023-2024

METHODOLOGY

As part of this study, the authors analysed data from the *Budget Book Volume-III (Detailed)* to compile grant data of the Health Department for fiscal year 2023-2024.

HEALTH BUDGET OVERVIEW

Out of a total current health budget of about Rs. 214.5 billion (not including the Rs. 13.26 billion for medical education), it is estimated that about Rs. 89.540 billion (41.7%) are earmarked as one-liner grants (see [Table 6](#)). About Rs. 71.6 billion is earmarked for salaries. A significant chunk of the budget is being disbursed as “grants” without any robust oversight mechanism or concrete linkage with outputs/KPIs. The practice undermines budget transparency and traceability and constrains the fiscal space for the government.

Table 6: List of single-line grants by the Health Department, Sindh, in fiscal year 2023-2024

No	Grant Title (Entity)	Grant Amount (PKR in Billion)
1	Sindh Institute of Urology and Transplantation (SIUT), Karachi	15.300
2	Pir Abdul Qadir Shah Jeelani Institute of Medical Sciences Gambat	6.000
3	Bone Marrow Transplantation at Dow University of Health Sciences, Karachi	0.060
4	Kidney Center, Karachi	0.200
5	Indus Hospital, Karachi	8.000
6	Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Center (JPMC), Karachi	11.217
7	PPHI Sindh	12.750
8	Shaheed Mohtarma Benazir Bhutto Institute of Trauma, Karachi	3.100
9	Syed Abdullah Shah Institute of Medical Science Sehwan Sharif, Jamshoro	1.850
10	Sindh Institute of Endoscopy and Gastrology (SIAG) at Dr. K.M. Pfau Civil Hospital, Karachi	0.750
11	Dialysis for Poor Patients	0.040
12	For Treatment of Patients @ Agha Khan University Hospital, Karachi	0.023
13	Afzaal Memorial Thalassemia Foundation, Karachi	0.044
14	Al Mustafa Trust, Sindh	0.015
15	Agha Welfare Trust (Agha Dialysis Center and Imam Clinic North Nazimabad)	0.025
16	Child Aid Association (NICH), Karachi	0.100
17	For Capital Cost of (230) Ambulances-SIEHS (one time)	0.655

18	Grant-in-Aid for Construction of Neuro-Psychiatric Center for Children, Malir, Karachi	0.250
19	Annual Rec. Grant For 100 Bedded Hospital/ Maternity Home Eid-Gah, Karachi	0.045
20	DNA For Sindh Forensic DNA and Serology Lab (ICCBS), University of Karachi	0.150
21	Fatimiyah Hospital Soldier Bazar, Karachi	0.050
22	For Treatment of Patients through the Gamma Knife Radiosurgery Center at DUHS	0.125
23	50 Bedded Hospital Gulistan-e-Johar, Karachi	0.045
24	Purchase of Hepatitis B Vaccine (birth dose)	0.183
25	Grant-in-Aid for Hemophilia Welfare Society	0.002
26	International Center for Chemical and Biological Sciences (ICCBS), Karachi	0.290
27	Grant-in-Aid for (one time) Replacing the Old Cyberknife with Latest Model	1.119
28	MBH Hospitals and Dispensaries Management Board	0.100
29	NIPA, Karachi	1.000
30	Operational Cost of (230) Ambulances-SIEHS	2.045
31	Operational Cost of (85) Ambulances-SIEHS	0.900
32	Treatment and Lab Investigation of COVID-19 Cases at Dow University, Karachi	0.024
33	Dr. Ziauddin Group of Hospitals for Liver Transplantation	0.006
34	Treatment of (20) Poor Patients (one time) for Treatment of Patients @ Dr. Ziauddin Hospital, Karachi	0.001
35	Indus Hospital PPP node	0.158
36	HANDS under PPP node	0.473
37	MERF under PPP node	0.965
38	For Remuneration of Polio Workers in Sindh	0.313
39	Layton Rahmatullah Benevolent Trust (LRBT)	0.080
40	Marie Adelaide Leprosy Centers in Sindh	0.050
41	Medicine of Blood Cancer Patients in Sindh	0.400
42	Treatment for Thalassemia in Various Health Facilities in Sindh	0.040
43	For ANF (MATRC) Centers (Karachi, Hyderabad and Sukkur)	0.100
44	Pakistan National Forum on Women's Health (PNFWH), Karachi	0.025
45	Strengthening of Chemico Bacteriological Lab. at Karachi and Sukkur (Ph-I)	0.154
46	Cancer Foundation	0.050
47	For Child Life Foundation, Karachi	1.600
48	Extension of CML Project for Other Cancer Diseases	0.400
49	Fatmid Foundation, Sindh	0.100
50	For Kashif Iqbal Thalassemia Care Trust, Karachi	0.050
51	Grant-in-Aid for Nimra, Jamshoro	0.122
52	Nigahbaan to Maintain the Surgical Unit at Civil Hospital Khi	0.100
53	Patients Welfare Association (PWA) at CHK	0.100

54	Prevalence, Research and Possible Treatment of Breast Cancer in Province	0.020
55	Grant-in-Aid for Umair Sana Foundation, Karachi	0.022
56	Women and Children Medical Care Trust (Women Hospital Shikarpur)	0.200
57	Preen Rasool Thalassemia Care Trust Qasimabad Hyd (PRTCT)	0.030
58	Procurement of (02) Robotic Surgical System at Lyari General Hospital, Karachi	1.751
59	Field Isolation and Vaccination Center Established at Karachi Expo Center	0.142
60	Community Midwifery Training Program at Koochi Goth Hospital, Karachi	0.022
61	Medical Treatment of Various Patients on Government Expenses	0.279
62	Patients Suffering from Auto Immune Disease	0.100
63	Purchase of Plant and Machinery	1.000
64	Purchase of Furniture and Fixtures	0.250
65	Sindh Institute of Cardiovascular Diseases (Hyderabad, Sehwan, Karachi x2, Khairpur, Larkana, Mithi, SBA, Sukkur, TMK)	6.420
66	National Institute of Cardiovascular Disease, Karachi	7.060
67	National Institute of Blood Disease (NIBD) and Bone Marrow Transplantation, Karachi	0.500
	TOTAL	89.540

Source: Authors' analysis of Sindh's Health Department budget for FY 2023-24